

Complexes of Cuprous Bromide with Primary Amines in Non-Aqueous Media

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Compounds of cuprous bromide with aromatic primary mono- and di-amines have been prepared in nonpolar solvents; their properties have been studied and structures discussed.

Though a few complexes¹⁻⁵ of Cu(I) have been prepared in aqueous or hydrochloric acid medium, no work on the formation of complexes of cuprous bromide with amines and heterocyclic bases in nonaqueous media appears to have been reported in the literature. The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the formation of the compounds of cuprous bromide with amines in nonaqueous media.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of 'extra pure' quality. Ethyl acetate was dried over calcium chloride for several days and distilled twice before use.

Anhydrous cuprous bromide and the amine were dissolved separately in ethyl acetate and the complexes prepared by adding an excess of the amine solution to that of the cuprous bromide, when a precipitate was formed; in some cases, however, the precipitate separated on addition of anhydrous benzene or anhydrous ether to the mixture. It was filtered, the precipitate washed free of the amine with ethyl acetate, dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride and analysed.

Copper was estimated as the α -benzoin oxime complex $Cu(C_{14}H_{11}O_2N)$ and bromine as silver bromide by Piria and Schiff's method. In a few cases nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method and carbon and hydrogen by micro-analytical methods.

General Properties.—All the compounds are characteristically coloured, semicrystalline powder, and fairly stable in dry air at the room temperature. These dissolve in dilute acids but decompose when treated with strong acids. The compounds are insoluble in benzene, ether, CCl_4 , and EtOH and partially soluble in dioxane and acetone. Monoamine complexes are partially soluble and diamine complexes are insoluble in ethyl acetate. When heated, some of them decompose without melting and some with melting (cf. Table I).

1. Straumanis and Circulis, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1936, 230, 65.
2. Foester and Blankenberg, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 4428.
3. Jones and Kennar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 711.
4. Claude R. Smith (To the United States of America as represented by the Secretary, of Agriculture) U.S. 2, 512, 689, June 27, 1950.
5. *Idem.*, *ibid.*, 2, 534, 835, Dec. 19, 1950.
6. Rueggeberg et al., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1222.

TABLE I

Name of compound of SARJU, with	Colour	M.P.	%Copper		%Bromine		%Nitrogen		%Carbon		%Hydrogen		Formula
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	
α -Naphthyl- amine	Brownish Black	226°d	22.19	22.17	28.20	27.91	4.80	4.88	..	..	..	..	CuBr(C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂)
β -Naphthylamine	Black	221°d	22.34	22.17	27.52	27.91	..	..	41.40	41.84	3.21	3.14	CuBr(C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂)
Aniline	Shining Black	123°d	25.35	26.84	32.64	33.79	5.80	5.91	..	..	..	..	CuBr(C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂)
<i>p</i> -Anisidine	Black	159°	23.20	23.83	28.82	29.99	5.15	5.25	..	..	..	..	CuBr(CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂)
<i>o</i> -Anisidine	Black	161°	23.65	23.83	29.21	29.99	..	..	31.71	31.50	3.31	3.37	CuBr(CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂)
<i>m</i> -Anisidine	Black	210°d	23.42	23.89	29.01	29.99	5.35	5.25	..	..	..	..	CuBr(CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂)
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	Black	158°d	24.98	25.35	32.00	31.92	5.50	5.58	..	..	..	..	CuBr(CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂)
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	Black	183°d	25.60	25.35	32.41	31.92	5.48	5.58	..	..	..	..	CuBr(CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂)
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	Black	151°d	24.26	25.35	31.45	31.92	5.46	5.58	..	..	..	..	CuBr(CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂)
<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	Black	165°d	21.92	22.63	31.80	28.51	4.90	4.99	..	..	..	..	CuBr(H ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ OC ₂ H ₅)
<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine	Black	204°d	22.32	22.63	31.20	28.51	4.91	4.99	..	..	..	..	CuBr(H ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ OC ₂ H ₅)
<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	Black	162°	22.20	22.63	31.31	28.51	..	..	..	..	..	..	CuBr(H ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ OC ₂ H ₅)
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	sky blue	122°	24.80	25.35	31.15	31.92	7.21	6.98	..	..	..	..	CuBr(C ₆ H ₃ .CH ₃ NH ₂)
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	Brownish Black	310°d	24.21	25.52	31.40	32.05	..	..	34.20	33.63	3.28	3.20	2C ₇ H ₇ (CH ₃)NH ₂ C ₆ H ₅ (CH ₃)NH ₂
Benidine	Black	251°d	27.42	26.91	31.12	32.50	5.71	5.94	..	..	..	..	2C ₇ H ₇ (H ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂)
<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine	Dark grey	154°d	32.68	32.15	39.96	40.48	7.40	7.13	18.54	18.22	2.21	2.02	2C ₆ H ₄ (NH ₂) ₂
<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	Black	218°d	32.52	32.15	40.22	40.48	..	..	..	..	..	..	2C ₆ H ₄ (NH ₂) ₂
<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine	Black	326°d	32.81	32.15	40.92	40.48	..	..	18.51	18.22	2.30	2.02	2C ₆ H ₄ (NH ₂) ₂
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	Violet	137°	24.30	23.98	30.24	30.12	5.32	5.27	..	..	..	..	2C ₇ H ₇ (H ₂ N)(OCH ₃ H ₃ C)- C ₆ H ₅ (OCH ₃ NH ₂)

°d denotes decomp. temp.

Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes with α -naphthylamine, *o*-phenetidine, *m*-anisidine, and *o*-tolidine were determined; all of them were found diamagnetic.

IR spectra of complexes with *m*-anisidine and *o*-phenetidine were recorded by Perkin-Elmer Infracord. However, only a few stretching frequencies (Table II) could be assigned with reasonable certainty as the spectrum is of very complex nature. In both the cases a strong and broad peak near 3400 cm.^{-1} (stretching frequency of bonded aromatic primary amines appears at $3410\text{-}3470 \text{ cm.}^{-1}$)⁷ confirms the co-ordination through nitrogen of aromatic amine and there is no structural change in the ligand during complex formation except co-ordination between nitrogen and cuprous ion.

TABLE II

With <i>m</i> -anisidine		With <i>o</i> -Phenetidine	
Stretching frequency	Remarks	Stretching frequency	Remarks
990, 860, 780	C-H Bend in benzene ring	860, 742, 675	C-H Bend in benzene ring
1560, 1510	N-H Bend	1510	N-H Bend
3450	NH ₂ bonded	3460	NH ₂ bonded
1260	C-N stretch	1285, 1235, 1160	C-N stretch
1595, 1480, 950	ring vibration aromatic hydrocarbon	1595, 1490	ring vibration aromatic hydrocarbon
1190	-C-O-C stretch	918	-C-O-C stretch
1450	C-H Bend in C=C-H	1450	C-C-H Bend
1385	-CH ₃ sym. Bend	1385	-CH ₃ sym. stretch
		2990	-CH ₃ sym. stretch

DISCUSSION

From the analytical data the ratio of Cu: Br: Organic base was found to be 1 : 1 : 1 in the case of a monoamine and 1 : 1 : $\frac{1}{2}$ with a diamine. Although from physico-chemical studies Wartenberg⁸ and Jellinek⁹ have shown the molecular formula of cuprous bromide as Cu₂Br₂, the complex may be simply represented as

in the case of a primary monoamine, and

in the case of a primary diamine.

7. West, "Chemical Applications of Spectroscopy, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York; Vol. 9, pp. 516, 564; 1956.

8. Z. Electrochem., 1922, 26, 984.

9. Z. physikal. Chem., 1929, 143, 58.

In the crystals, however, there may be polymerisation leading to Cu(I) attaining a tetrahedral co-ordination, as in the case of $\text{Et}_3\text{As.CuX}^{10}$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{P.CuX}^{11}$ (where X is a halide) which are tetrameric.

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